

VIBRATION MEASUREMENT OF FIBER COMPOSITE BEAM USING INTERFEROMETRIC MICHELSON FIBER OPTIC SENSOR WITH DIGITAL PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, a digital processing method is used for the passive phase-demodulation technique with 3x3 passive interferometric Michelson fiber optic sensor (MFOS) to measure the vibration response of a fiber composite beam. The sensor is adhered to the surface of a cantilever beam to measure its deflection under free vibration condition with a low frequency. The strain response is also obtained by the electrical strain gauge mounted to the surface of the specimen. This is used for comparing the calculated input phase from the MFOS outputs. Experimental results show that the digital processing presented here has applicability to the vibration measurement.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber optic strain sensors are expected as powerful devices in smart structures. Especially, interferometric sensors have high sensitivity and many experiments using them have been conducted. But interferometric sensors have the characteristic problem that the output response is cyclic in nature. That is, their outputs may have the same value for several strain conditions. The quadrature phase detection technique is the most effective solution method and there are two approaches to the technique, that is, one is the active approach using the complicate analogue circuits with the PZT modulator and another is the passive approach. Considering the simplicity of the equipment, the latter is used with using digital processing which is based on the simple interferometric theory.

DIGITAL PROCESSING

The optical output intensity of 3x3 MFOS can be described generally as : [1]

$$I_1=I_0[1+K\sin(\phi)] \tag{1}$$

$$I_2=I_0[1+K\cos(\phi)] \tag{2}$$

where I_0 is related to the input optical power, K is the fringe visibility, and ϕ is the optical phase change due to varying strain. In Eqns (1) and (2) I_0 and K are constants, and then ϕ can be calculated in the digital computer using two inverse functions as:

$$\phi=\cos^{-1}(CV(I_1))-\pi/2 \tag{3}$$

$$\phi=\cos^{-1}(CV(I_2)) \tag{4}$$

$$CV(I)=(I-I_0)/K \tag{5}$$

In general Eqns (3) and (4) are restricted within the domain of the trigonometric functions, for example $3\pi/2$ cannot be obtained by using \cos^{-1} . Once the relative phase change $\Delta\phi$ is obtained, can be computed by the summation of relative phase changes. Let the initial phase be ϕ_0 and two outputs of 3x3 MFOS be changed into I_1^* and I_2^* . From output I_1^* , $\Delta\phi$ can be calculated by either of two equations as:

$$\Delta\phi=\cos^{-1}((CV(I_1^*))+\phi_0)-\pi/2 \tag{6}$$

$$\Delta\phi=5\pi/2-\cos^{-1}((CV(I_1^*))+\phi_0) \tag{7}$$

From output I_2^* , $\Delta\phi$ can be calculated in the similar manner as:

$$\Delta\phi=\cos^{-1}((CV(I_2^*))+\phi_0) \tag{8}$$

$$\Delta\phi=2\pi-\cos^{-1}((CV(I_2^*))+\phi_0) \tag{9}$$

True value of $\Delta\phi$ can be selected when the same values can be obtained in Eqns (6), (7), (8) and (9). Note that absolute values of four equations described above are used and so the information of increasing or decreasing in the phase change is lost. In measuring the beam vibration, it makes a serious question. Fig.1 shows that the simulation result of 3x3 MFOS outputs to free vibration is calculated by using Eqns (1) and (2). Paying attention to changes in outputs of 3x3 MFOS in Fig.1, both outputs I_1 and I_2 must change their each direction when the beam response is maximum (point A) or minimum (point B). Let this point be called the turning point (TP). It is found that a sign of $\Delta\phi$ is constant in an interval between one TP and the next TP, for example a sign of $\Delta\phi$ is negative between A and B and then after B it changes into positive. But as this criterion is not always satisfied in practice, such another criterion must be added that the change in the quantity of $\Delta\phi$ is nearly equal to zero at A or B. In converting $\Delta\phi$ to strain change, the strain sensitivity G is used:

$$G = \frac{\Delta\phi}{\epsilon L}, \quad (10)$$

where ϵ is strain change, L is the gauge length of 3x3 MFOS. The unit of G is radian per micro-strain per meter. G can be obtained experimentally by the tensile test.

SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The 3x3 MFOS system is shown in Fig.2. The source is a laser diode PT-4051-830 wavelength=830nm (SEASTAR OPTICS INC.). A multi laser driver GSB-3000 (GROBAL ELECTRONIC INDUSTRY Co.,Ltd.) which can keep the temperature around the laser diode constant and has an automatic power control (APC) was used for its power source. Single mode fiber (FS-SN-4224 3M) is used in the system. The laser diode and the MFOS bonded to the surface of the specimen are connected with a 3x3 single-mode coupler L33S82D (SIFAM LIMITED) by Fibrlok™ (3M) fiber splicers. The output signals are preamplified and fed to the computer through the A/D converter board. The electrical strain gauge is also mounted to the surface of the specimen. This was used for comparing the calculated strain response which is obtained from the MFOS outputs.

STRAIN SENSOR CALIBRATION

A static tensile test was conducted for the specimen with the MFOS bonded to its surface in order to check the strain sensitivity G for the MFOS. The MFOS outputs for the test are shown in Fig.3. The strain-phase response of MFOS is shown in Fig.4 which is obtained by counting fringes in Fig.3. It was obtained that the relation between the strain ϵ and the phase f as shown in Fig.4 is exactly expressed by a linear function $f(\epsilon, \phi)$, where the coefficient of correlation is 0.99. Thus, the strain sensitivity G can be calculated from this tangent of $f(\epsilon, \phi)$ and the fiber optic sensor gauge length using Eqn (10):

$$G = 1.86 \times 10^7 \text{ (rad/m)} \quad (11)$$

It was confirmed that the calculated strain sensitivity G in Eqn (11) was nearly equal to the experimental one by another author [1].

VIBRATION MEASUREMENT

Using the MFOS system shown in Fig.2, the deflection of the specimen under the free vibration excitation with a low frequency was measured. The MFOS outputs are shown in Fig.5 and it is found that the outputs in Fig.5 almost resemble in shape the theoretical ones in Fig.1. But there is the difference of the amplitude change between in Fig.5 and in Fig.1, and as K in Eqns (1), (2) and (5) is not suppose constant, then K is replaced by $K(t)$. $K(t)$ can be calculated as:

$$K(t) = \sqrt{\frac{I_1'^2 + I_2'^2 - 2I_1' I_2' \cos(\phi)}{\sin^2(\phi)}}, \quad (12)$$

$$I_1' = K(t) \sin(\phi), \quad (13)$$

$$I_2' = K(t) \cos(\phi). \quad (14)$$

Considering the above-mentioned facts, the calculated strain response using digital processing is shown in Fig.6. The electrical strain gauge output is also shown in Fig.6 for comparing the result of the MFOS. It is shown in Fig.6 that the MFOS has much ability for vibration measurement and the digital processing described here is considered as the effective method to analyze the MFOS outputs.

CONCLUSION

To measure the vibration of a fiber composite beam using the fiber optic sensor, the passive approach with the digital processing was examined and the MFOS system based on it was constructed. In the experimental result of free vibration measurement, it was shown that the digital processing technique presented here had applicability to the vibration measurement. However as this processing was so heavy for a 16bit computer (CPU 80286) used in this system, a much powerful computer with high speed and large capacity will be needed if the real-time processing for measurement of vibration with higher frequencies will be performed.

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REFERENCE

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Figure 1. Theoretical outputs of 3x3 MFOs

Figure 2. 3x3 MFOS system

Figure 3. Outputs of 3x3 MFOS for the tensile test

Figure 4. Strain-phase response of 3x3 MFOS

Figure 5. An experimental result of 3x3 MFOS

Figure 6. Calculated strain response of 3x3 MFOS

INSPECTION AND NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION
